

ASSOCIATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY INTO HUMAN CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract. Success in any area of life requires the ability to learn and apply knowledge in creative and effective ways. The article discusses issues of adapting the educational process to new technologies.

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Whether you provide education in a school, university or business, developing your students' cognitive functions is your number one priority. However, many educational environments today are insufficient. The learning process provided by traditional methods is unstimulating for students and makes learning time-consuming.

It is well known that students are more capable of learning when they complete tasks independently. However, most training exercises are done orally. Although visual images and verbal instructions can be a useful way of presenting information, they are not highly effective learning tools.

The human brain is only capable of remembering a small percentage of information—even less when the student is not stimulated. As a result, the best method of learning in the current paradigm is repetition.

“Virtual reality gives us the opportunity to scale the learning process and make it more dynamic and exciting. A relatively small virtual device can even function as an entire scientific laboratory.”

What does virtual reality do to the brain?

Scientific research in neuroscience and psychology has shown that the brain creates a mental map of the environment based on information that is absorbed by the five senses. Subsequently, the information becomes our perception of reality, and the more information we take on board, the better our cognition develops. When we see something familiar, the brain predicts what will happen next.

However, when the brain has no practical experience in a given situation, what prediction will it make? The response will be based on information that is stored in memory.

Virtual reality can rewire the brain and improve neural connections needed for learning and memory. In a simulated environment, the brain sees and does exactly what it

needs to do—it doesn't fill in the blanks. As a result, students and trainees can learn faster and more efficiently.

“Virtual reality technology can provide more effective learning at a lower cost and in less time than many traditional teaching methods.”

Virtual reality titles are designed to completely immerse users in a virtual simulation. Their vision, hearing, smell and touch are absent in the real world, so the brain considers the virtual world to be real. Thanks to this, cells take in information and create “schemas” that influence how students will react to real-life situations. Additionally, new synapses are formed that can help students improve learning in other areas of their lives.

Virtual reality improves memory.

In the 1880s, the eminent German psychologist Hermann Ebbinghaus showed how difficult it is for people to remember information. He called his hypothesis the 'forgetting curve'. In educational environments where oral and image-based teaching methods are used, the average person will forget 50% of the information within the first hour. The next day we forget 70 percent of the details, and without retelling a month later we remember only 10 percent of the information.

One of the most important attributes of virtual reality is the ability to evoke emotional responses. Since the brain believes that the virtual simulation is a real situation, the emotional reactions that are triggered enhance the user's learning ability.

The study involved 40 participants who were asked to complete a task using a virtual reality headset and then use their own coordination again. When participants used virtual reality headsets, the results improved memory performance by 8.8%.

One intriguing area of exploration is the influence of AI on human consciousness. As AI systems become more advanced, capable of performing complex tasks, and even exhibiting human-like behaviors, it raises questions about how it may shape our understanding of consciousness. In this article, we will delve into different aspects of this topic and explore the possible implications of AI on human consciousness.

1. Defining Consciousness:

To start, it's crucial to define what we mean by "consciousness." Consciousness refers to our subjective awareness, our ability to perceive, reason, experience emotions, and have a sense of self. It is often associated with qualities such as self-awareness, intentionality, and the ability to reflect upon our own mental states.

2. AI and Cognitive Abilities:

AI technology has made significant advancements in mimicking human cognitive abilities, learning from vast amounts of data, and making decisions based on patterns and algorithms. While AI systems can perform tasks that previously required human intelligence, they lack the subjective experience and self-awareness that characterize human consciousness. However, some argue that future AI systems might exhibit qualities akin to consciousness, leading to debates about what constitutes true consciousness.

3. AI as a Tool for Studying Consciousness:

AI can also serve as a tool for exploring and understanding human consciousness. By studying how AI systems operate and behave, researchers can gain insights into our own cognitive processes and consciousness. Simulating certain aspects of human consciousness through AI models allows scientists to test hypotheses and build theories about consciousness that can be hard to study through traditional scientific methods.

4. Ethical Considerations:

As AI evolves, ethical dilemmas arise concerning its potential impact on human consciousness. For instance, if AI systems become advanced enough to exhibit human-like emotions, should we grant them some form of moral consideration? Furthermore, if AI surpasses human cognitive abilities, what implications could this have for our own sense of identity and purpose? These questions raise important considerations about our relationship with AI and how it may shape our understanding of ourselves.

5. Social and Psychological Impact:

The integration of AI into various aspects of our lives, such as personal assistant applications or social media algorithms, can also influence human consciousness. AI systems often personalize content and recommendations based on our preferences and behaviors. This can shape our beliefs, values, and perceptions, potentially impacting our individual consciousness and collective social consciousness.

6. The Future Outlook:

While AI's influence on human consciousness is still largely speculative, it is clear that this is an area of significant interest and inquiry. As AI continues to progress, scientists, philosophers, and ethicists will continue to explore the implications and importance of AI on our understanding of consciousness.

In conclusion, the influence of artificial intelligence on human consciousness is a complex and evolving subject. While AI can replicate certain cognitive functions, it lacks the subjective experience and self-awareness that define human consciousness. Nonetheless, AI serves as a valuable tool for studying consciousness and raises important ethical and societal considerations. As we navigate the development and integration of AI into our lives, it is crucial to reflect on how it may shape our understanding and experience of consciousness. A study conducted by the Department of Psychology at the University of Regensburg found that the most effective teaching methods using virtual reality are stimulating the user's emotions. The researchers also made a connection between learning curves and how present or engaged users were during their experience. Students who are not engaged retain less information and are less prepared to apply their existing knowledge to real-world situations.

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